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A Study on Religion and Everyday Life in Rural Setting

Abstract: Religion continues to play a pivotal role in the human society. Human beings often take refuge in the religious practices to overcome the problems of the mundane life. There are many who also perform different religious rites to find salvation. Social changes and rapid improvement in the technological field have also influenced the way of practicing religion in Society. Sacred practices are seen to be the manifestation of the religion. The globalization and mobility also lead to spread of secularization of religion. Yet people from different religion practices it in their own way in day to day life. This study was made in a rural context keeping in view the changes that took place because of increased mobility and growing secularization. This empirical study was conducted in a village situated near Indo-Bangladesh border of West Bengal, an eastern state of India. Descriptive research design was followed as the intention was to gather knowledge about the religious practices of a particular religious community. Thirty samples were collected. Sample survey technique was used to collect data on perception of individuals on religion and their practices in daily life. The study showed that majority of the respondents managed time to participate in religious activities. Even though the perception on differences between spirituality and religion was not very clear, yet they felt that they were religious. In fact, majority of them were exposed to the place of prayer and religious practices since early childhood. They also opined that they received divine intervention in their lives at the hour of crisis.

Keywords: Religion, faith, spirituality, scripture, God, worship

Introduction

Religion is an important aspect of social life in human society. It is really difficult to predict the timing of the rise of religion in society. Human beings are involved in different religious practices to establish relationship with God. God is the considered as the refuge of millions of people. Even though there are different religions and practices to worship God or the Divine. Religion provides an outlet for overcoming sorrow, anxiety, distress, prejudices and blame associated with the mundane activities of life. Common people generally develop virtues like compassion, kindness and sympathy through the reading of religious scriptures and involvement in religious practices. It also helps people to overcome the prejudices that they have in their lives. Religion helps people to grow in knowledge, faith and love. This ultimately leads to the way of

spirituality. It is often argued that attaining the spirituality should be the goal of human life. It is through the religious practices and participation in religious activities, people form indomitable and unshakable faith in their respective belief. Every religion on earth helps the people to understand the meaning of life. It also provides a roadmap to be followed in life.

A famous sociologist Emile Durkheim, in his book “The Elementary Forms of Religious Life: A Study in Religious Sociology”, commented that “religion is a unified system of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, that is, things that are set apart and forbidden” (Durkheim, 1915). Thus, religion involves the belief in the sacred activities of men. The common people are often disturbed and overwhelmed by the external difficulties of life and faith in God helps to toil in the life with the expectation of justice from Him. Almost in every society, some form of religious practices is found. Common people not only practices but also involve themselves in preaching from a deep conviction that it will lead to salvation. The notion of heaven and earth is also common in majority of the religions.

In society, one may come across that some individuals also leave their families behind for joining a religious order. Hence, religion continues to be a pivotal part of modern society. In fact idea of religion includes both external piety and interior spirituality. The progression of the science and technology has brought rapid changes in the last century and advanced societies are tilting towards the idea of secular practices. Yet it cannot be said to be grown in wisdom and morality (Mascarenhas, 2018). It is also needed to remember that even though the religious practices in a particular religion is followed by both men and women, but need for religion is based on the nature and personalities of males and females (Davie, 2007).

The existence of religious practices in the human society can be found since time immemorial. In every human society, religious practices are found. In fact almost all citizens in Indian society report religious affiliation. Religion provides them a sense of belonging and they remain affiliated. It is also stated that involvement in the religious practices provides an individual inner peace. Positive feelings that emanate from the religious practices also contribute to the wellbeing of a person (Taylor, 2012, p. 5). It is also said that common people have many problems throughout their lives and sometimes the problems are not solved at all. Burden of problems often leads people to take unreasonable decisions and steps in life. It is seen that people who are religiously inclined generally negotiate with the problems in a better way. Though the ordinary people are living in a world of relativity and uncertainty, yet there is an inherent desire to inquire about the existence (Hunt, 2005, p. 1). It is also true that people go for pilgrimage for fulfilling a religious purpose. They visit local shrines, places of religious significance for obtaining solace and peace.

Many individuals go alone, others in groups to perform religious rituals. Modernity indeed changed the way of reaching and performing but the very essence of religion remain more or less unchanged in human society. Belief in supernatural power gives the ordinary people a sense of purpose in life. It is to be noted that expressions of beliefs do vary amongst the people but the goal of such practices remain same. People get religious experiences through these practices. Religions help to establish harmony in life. Some noted religious commentators like Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyya argue that religion has so many meanings and often contradictory to one another but its existence is found everywhere. Religion is natural and universal social institution.

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Justification of the study

Indian society is going through a transitional change. The people's religious practices are also changing. Modernity has invaded even the remotest parts of Indian Society. The presence of technology has brought a sea change in the lives of ordinary people. Even though the traditional religious practices are hardly adhered to but people perform religion. The people of West Bengal, a state of India, irrespective of their religious beliefs celebrate different religious festivals. The presence of place of worship in very neighbourhood bears the testimony of the religious practices of ordinary people.

It is pertinent to look at how ordinary people think about religion, their religious practices in their mundane life and their perception about belief. It is a fact that though majority of the people practice religion but this is also considered as a private affair of an individual. They often do it in their households. Many visit respective places of worship which differs according to belief system. The issue of religion in everyday life hardly finds its place in the academic deliberations. The study aims at throwing lights on the belief system and religious practices of common people.

Review of literature

The review is needed as it helps the researcher get familiar with the existing knowledge. Every research is taken up with the intention of adding new knowledge which is dependent on the past knowledge. Review of literature generally helps the researcher to understand the field and gain knowledge. In this study, two books have been reviewed.

Davie (2007) shows in her book 'Sociology of Religion' that religion is no longer confined to the private domain but is gradually finds its place in the public agenda. It can be also termed as the return of religion and has brought a change in perception of people regarding its existence in the west society. It is shown how people in the modern society perceive religion and spirituality. A thorough study was done in different European countries to understand the changing role of church and state in the context of ensuring wellbeing and place of religion in society. The author deals with the origins of sociology of religion along with the impact of secularization or religious practices of people.

Religion has changed a lot because of modernity and globalization. Different practices in European countries have been highlighted to demonstrate the comparative perspectives on religion that are prevalent in Europe. The issue of minorities in the society have been also touched upon. The connection between modernity and religion has been dealt with. The relevance of religion in the context of modernity is also discussed.

In spite of invasion of modernity, the increasing influence of religion on world affairs and lives of individuals has been deliberated in the book. Even the degree of religiousness and practices also differs between men and women. Women are found to be more inclined towards performing religion. The author also shows the importance of religion on the thinking of the founding fathers of sociology. Both the

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American and European contexts have been compared to show the significance of rational choice theory in America and secularization theory in Europe.

The Contribution of Weber, Durkheim in the field of sociology of religion and Marx's perspective on religion are also discussed to bring about the diverse opinions on the role of religion in society. It is to be noted that the author tried to find out the relationship between social structure and religious beliefs through highlighting the works of Weber.

A chapter in the book is focused on the place of religion in everyday life. The attempt is made to show how the people in the modern society looked at religion. The importance of religion at the time of birth and death has been explored. The growing importance of secularization in European society has initiated a drastic change in the outlook of people regarding religion. The state has taken over the welfare activities of church. This has also caused a conflict in many European societies and initially pushed the religion into the private domain of individuals. The author correctly pointed out that the separation of state and Church is also not uniformly followed in European nations. But political upheavals and economic recession in the last part of twentieth century brings back the role of Church in the welfare services in the society. Hence, religion again returns to the public domain.

Even though religion in everyday life declines due to progress of science and gradual separation of state and Church in Europe, the author shows that the changes have influenced the attitude of people. A large section of people disassociate themselves from organized religion but at the same time they do not oppose it. It is concluded that there are ample evidence of marginal religious involvement of people in European societies.

McGuire (2008) in her book "Lived Religion: Faith and practice in Everyday Life" focuses on the ordinary people's religion and spiritual practices in their everyday lives. She argues that sociologists believed that religion has enduring characteristics but they have failed to consider it as an object evolved out of historical, socio-cultural discourses and processes. She mentions also that studies have been conducted on religion from the point of view of religious institutions and organizations rather than on religious practices done by individual at their personal domain. These studies conducted by sociologists also assumed that religious practices of an individual will be dictated and determined by his/her religious affiliation. Hence, people belonging to a particular religious organization will follow the prescribed religious practices uniformly.

McGuire differs and says that the way religion is practiced at the individual level varies and it is multifaceted. She claims that people at their individual level engage in hybrid behaviours. She states that religion is often thought to be dictated by the religious institutions but religion in the everyday life can be only understood by focussing on the religious activities performed at the individual level. She comments that lived religious experiences are complex subjects and it cannot be captured through quantitative surveys adopted by sociologists. She tries to convey that sociological studies of past on religion could only bring partial truth but attempts should be made to go beyond the definitional boundaries to understand the truth associated with religion in everyday life. She puts forward an explanation that practices of religion in everyday life and lived religion can be best understood by not giving much importance to the behaviour or

activities of people in their respective religious places but rather focussing on their religious practices at their households.

In order to get the meaning of lived religion, McGuire asks to look beyond the conventional spaces like church, temple and synagogues etc. In fact, the home shrines, moments spent at private chapels which are known as non-institutional religious and spiritual places are equally important to comprehend how faith is practiced at everyday life. McGuire states that lived religion is not a straight forward concept rather multifaceted and diverse. Individuals not only express religion in the life but also experience it. They are also influenced by the contemporary religious identities. She says that there is tendency to study religion from the above whereas the real meaning can be found by adopting bottom up approach in the study of religion. McGuire argues that lived religion of an individual is not constructed within individually but rather the individuals are influenced by the experiences that they share with others. It is product of inter subjective reality rather than the outcome of subjective feelings of an individual. She interprets that religion is the belief and mind plays a role in manifesting it in daily life. Individuals share meaning of religion in the social and cultural contexts. The practices are also followed religiously.

McGuire uses case studies to substantiate her arguments. But it should be noted that use of extensive case studies are not free from problematic consequences. It is stated that individuals often go beyond the official doctrine of performing the religion. She introduces concepts like 'syncretism', 'play' and 'hybridity' to depict the religious world to understand the meaning that her subjects under her study tied to convey. She also deals with the religious identity and comments that religious identity is formed through the family, ethnicity, gender and occupation. Even she says that gender plays a role in the practices of religion in everyday life. The lived religion can be only understood if the social relationships, class concept and generational preferences are considered. The idea of lived religion can be comprehended only through the understanding of the individuals and agencies of religion.

Objectives of the study

1. To understand the perception of individuals on religion with reference to their beliefs.
2. To describe the religious practices of the individuals.
3. To find out the place of religion in the daily lives of the individuals.

Research methodology

The research methodology helps the researcher to understand the problem by outlining the methods which will ultimately fulfill the objectives of specific study. Proper understanding for research methodology helps a researcher to develop an effective research design.

This particular research study followed descriptive research design. The aim was to describe the religious belief and practices of the people in the context of religion in everyday life. Descriptive research design is chosen as the aim was to show what and not with how and why (Ramamurthy, 2012, p. 54) . The selection of

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research methodology is dependent on issues being investigated. The researcher opted for quantitative data which is deductive and value free to meet the objectives of the research.

Representative samples were drawn from the population. The researcher used sample survey. Sample survey is effective in obtaining information from the population by investing minimum cost, time and labour (Singh, Bhatia, Kaur, & Kaur, 2009, p. 78). This research was conducted in Hathkhola Gram Panchayat under Chapra Block in Nadia, West Bengal. This village is the home of three major religious communities- Muslims, Christians and Hindus. Just before partition of undivided India and immediately after partition of India, hundreds of Hindu and Christian families migrated from East Pakistan to this village. Christians have even shifted their place of worship and settled down in this village. The village is very near to international Indo- Bangladesh border.

The researcher first tried to prepare the sampling frame. The research was conducted on the people practicing Christianity. The respondents of the research belonged to the members of the ‘*Kristobhakter Sahay Maria*’ Church located at Ranabandha village in Hathkhola Gram Panchayat. More than three hundred Christian families reside in the village and as per census of 2011; there were 7,164 people in that village. The researcher approached the Parish Priest of the Church to access the names of the church members. The name of the Church members was found from the register maintained by the Church. The Church maintains family diary of each family. Hence, the universe of this study was finite. The researcher opted for thirty samples from the population. Simple random sampling method was used to select the sample from the sampling frame. Trippett’s table of random numbers was used to select respondents. The researcher used a Survey method to collect quantitative data. In this study, an interviewer-mediated survey was applied. The interviewer used a paper schedule to obtain data from the respondents. The survey schedule consisted of close-ended questions.

The data collected from different respondents through survey were analyzed by using univariate statistical analysis. Simple descriptive statistics like frequency and percentage were used to show the responses. Graphical representation was also given for easy understanding. A pilot study was conducted to understand the validity and reliability of the survey schedule. The researcher followed steps to ensure confidentiality. Participants were asked to sign a document indicating informed consent, informed consent forms have been stored in a safe locked cabinet and Participants were assured of their rights to privacy.

Data analysis and interpretation

Age distribution of the respondents

Age plays a role in the religious activities of in life. It is generally said that aged people are more religious. It is also found that young and old people engage in religious activities.

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Table 1 Age Distribution

Serial No.	Age Distribution (in years)	Number	Percentage
1.	18-22	7	23.33
2.	23-27	4	13.33
3.	28-32	6	20.00
4.	33-37	2	6.67
5.	38-42	-	-
6.	43-47	3	10.00
7.	48-52	2	6.67
8.	53-57	1	3.33
9.	58-62	2	6.67
10.	63 and above	3	10.00
	Total	30	100.00

The above table 1 shows that 23.33% of the respondent belongs to the age group of 18-22 years, 13.33% of them belong to 23-27 years of age and 20% of them are in the age group of 28-32 years. Hence, majority of the respondents under this study are between 18 years and 32 years.

Educational status

It is believed that there is a relationship between education and religious practices. Even the attendance in the religious places in some countries is dictated by educational level.

Table 2 Educational Level of the Respondents

Serial No.	Education	Number	Percentage
1.	Primary	7	23.33
2.	Upper Primary	3	10.00
3.	Secondary	6	20.00
4.	Higher Secondary	8	26.67
5.	Graduation	5	16.67
6.	Post Graduate	1	3.33
	Total	30	100.00

The table 2 indicates that respondents under this study have different educational levels. 23.33% of them studied up to primary level. One fifth of them completed secondary level. More than one fourth (26.67%) finished higher secondary level and 16.67% studied up to graduation level.

Professions performing religion

Profession also plays a role in performing religion. As the study concentrated on the Christian community, they need to attend church services. Those who go far away for search of livelihood often face difficulty in managing time to attend. Hence, it was thought to be pertinent to know their profession.

Table 3 Profession

Serial No	Profession	Number	Percentage
1.	Agriculture	6	20.00
2.	Student	4	13.34
3.	Housewife	10	33.34
4.	Church Service	1	3.33
5.	Teaching	1	3.33
6.	Cooking in Hotels	3	10.00
7.	SHG	2	6.67
8.	Civic Volunteer	1	3.33
9.	Private Service	1	3.33
10.	Nursing	1	3.33
	Total	30	100.00

The table 3 indicates that respondents under this study belong to various professions. Majority of the respondents (33.34%) were housewives. One fifth of the respondents (20%) were engaged in agricultural activities. It can be seen that 13.33% of them were studying and rest of the respondents were involved in Self Help Groups (SHGs), private sector, civic volunteer in police department, nursing and teaching.

Commitment to religious teachings

This study is conducted among the believers of Christianity. Christians are exposed to religious teachings since early childhood. Christians generally pray in churches, attend catechism classes. They also attend church services.

Table 4 Commitment to religious teachings

Serial Number	Commitment to religious teachings	Number	Percentage
1.	Yes	29	96.67
2.	No	-	-
3.	Not Sure	1	3.33
	Total	30	100.00

The table 4 reveals that overwhelming number of respondents (96.67%) stated that they were committed to their religious teachings. Such commitment helps people to find a meaning in life. It can also have an influence in forming feelings, appropriate behaviours and maintaining mental health.

Active involvement in Religious Institution

Active involvement in religious institution can be assessed by the frequency of Church attendance. It is also evident from the membership in the Bible study group and prayer group. It was felt necessary to enquire from the respondents about their involvement.

Table 5 Active involvement in Religious Institution

Serial No.	Active Involvement in Religious Institution	Number	Percentage
1.	Yes	22	73.33
2.	No	8	26.67
	Total	30	100.00

The above table 5 indicates that 73.33% of the total respondents were actively involved in the religious institution. It may be interpreted that majority of the respondents were engaged in organizational religiousness and they participated actively in church services.

Consideration of oneself as religious person

Consideration of oneself as a religious person depends on the subjective feeling of an individual. This is generally shaped by the belief system. It was evident from the responses of the respondents that all respondents considered themselves as religious. It is pertinent to mention that even though who did not participate actively in church services, thought that they were religious.

Level of Religiousness

This level of religiosity is basically subjective in nature. It depends on religious affiliation, church attendance and respect of religious leaders.

Table 6 Level of Religiousness

Serial No.	Level of Religiousness	Number	Percentage
1.	Partially	9	30.00
2.	Moderately	5	16.67
3.	Very Much	14	46.67
4.	Not Known	2	6.66
	Total	30	100.00

The above table 6 reveals that 46.67% of the respondents perceived that their religious ties were very strong whereas 30% of them feel that they were partially attached to religion. The responses revealed the strength of religious beliefs amongst the respondents.

Spirituality and Religion carries same meaning

Spirituality and religion are not same. The way religion is practised in the world only shows that it is an institutionalised system. On the other hand, notion of spirituality denotes that the recognition of a feeling of something which is greater than oneself. In common parlance, spirituality and religion are used interchangeably. Hence, it was felt necessary to know from the respondents about their understanding.

Table 7 Spirituality and Religion carries same meaning

Serial Number	Spirituality and Religion carries same meaning	Number	Percentage
1.	Yes	8	26.67
2.	No	8	26.67
3.	Not Sure	14	46.66
	Total	30	100.00

The table 7 shows that 26.67% of the respondents felt that spirituality and religion were same whereas majority of the respondents (46.66%) thought that they did not have clear idea about the relationship between two terms. Their responses showed that there was absence of clarity in the context of understanding difference between spirituality and religion.

Visiting current place of worship

The visiting of place of worship is part and parcel of manifestation of religion. The respondents were asked to state the duration of visiting current place of worship.

Table 8 Duration of visiting current place of worship

Serial No.	Duration of visiting current place of worship	Number	Percentage
1.	1 year or less	1	3.33
2.	2-4 years	3	10.00
3.	10-19 years	5	16.67
4.	20 or more years	21	70.00
	Total	30	100.00

The table 8 shows that 70% of the respondents were visiting their current place of worship for more than twenty years. Nearly one sixth of the respondents were visiting the place of worship for a duration which ranged from ten years to nineteen years.

Paying contribution at place of worship

The keeping of church as place of prayer is considered as a vital issue by the members of the church. They bear the expenses of parish. It is important to ask the respondents about contribution made by them.

Table 9 Contribution at place of worship

Serial No.	Contribution at place of worship	Number	Percentage
1.	Yes	24	80.00
2.	No	6	20.00
	Total	30	100.00

The Table 9 indicates that 80% of the respondents contribute to the church. It should be noted that contribution to church is considered to a duty mentioned in the religious scripture of Holy Bible. The contribution made by respondents can be treated as the performance of religious duty.

Praying alone besides praying at place of worship

Even though in Christian community prayer with community people is preferred, many people also engage in prayer alone in their private domain.

Table 10 Praying Alone

Serial Number.	Praying alone	Number	Percentage
1.	Never	3	10.00
2.	Once in a day	11	36.67
3.	Several times in a day	2	6.67
4.	Several times in a week	2	6.66
5.	Several times in month	10	33.33
6.	Whenever feel necessity of Prayer	2	6.67
	Total	30	100.00

The table 10 reveals that more than one third of the respondents (36.67%) did pray alone. It was interesting to note that 33.33% of them also pray alone when they felt the necessity of prayer.

Reading Religious scripture

Christians follow Holy Bible. It is generally believed that formation of Christian beliefs come through the reading of scripture.

Table 11 Reading Religious scripture

Serial No.	Reading Religious Scripture	Number	Percentage
1.	Yes	20	66.67
2.	No	10	33.33
	Total	30	100.00

The Table 11 shows that 66.67% respondents read the religious scripture. It can be stated that Christianity is based on scripture. They were performing the religious duty.

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Frequency of Reading religious scripture

It is found that frequency of reading scriptures widely differs among the readers of religious books.

Table 12 Frequency of Reading Religious Scripture

Serial No.	Frequency of Reading Religious Scripture	Number	Percentage
1.	Daily	6	20.00
2.	Several Times in a week	5	16.67
3.	Several Times in a month	1	3.33
4.	Some Times in a year	8	26.67
5.	Not Applicable	10	33.33
	Total	30	100.00

The table indicates that only one fifth of the respondents read daily whereas 26.67% of them read the books sometimes in year. It is also important to note that only 16.67% of them read several times in a week. This shows that reading scripture varied among respondents. The scripture reading can be closely linked with the spiritual development. The reading may renew their mind.

Concept of God

Believers in Christianity often feel the omnipotent presence of God. The respondents were asked to define how they view God.

Table 13 Concept of God

Serial No.	Concept of God	Number	Percentage
1.	Ever present	19	63.33
2.	Distant	1	3.33
3.	Forgiving	10	33.34
	Total	30	100.00

The table 13 shows that 63.33% of the respondents felt that God was ever present and 33.34% of them considered God as forgiving. It can be said that such concepts of God not only help them to perform religious duties but also provide a roadmap in life.

Belief in Heaven and Hell on the basis of activities in life

Christians believe in heaven and hell. This is the indication of belief that there is a life after death. The concepts of heaven and hell carry the hope of afterlife which is based on the deeds performed during life time. In Christianity, there is a belief that people will be sent either to heaven or hell permanently on the judgement day. It was felt pertinent to enquire their thoughts on the issue.

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Table 14 Belief in Heaven and Hell on the Basis of activities in life

Serial No.	Belief in Heaven and Hell on the Basis of activities in life	Number	Percentage
1.	Yes	18	60.00
2.	No	5	16.67
3.	Don't Know	7	23.33
	Total	30	100.00

The table 14 reveals that majority of the respondents (60%)believed in heaven and hell. But a significant percentage of respondents (23.33%) are not sure about it whereas 16.67% of them did not believe in this concept.

Remembering God in the hour of crisis

Common people often face difficult situations in their life. It is also believed that remembering God in such situation will help one to overcome circumstances.

Table 15 Remembering God in the hour of crisis

Serial Number.	Remembering God in the hour of crisis	Number	Percentage
1.	Seldom	1	3.33
2.	Sometimes	2	6.67
3.	Often	1	3.33
4.	Always	26	86.67
	Total	30	100.00

The table 15 shows that overwhelming percentage of respondents (86.67%) remembered God when they faced crisis and crushing difficulties. This was indicative of the fact that most of them took refuge in God at the difficult times of life.

Feelings regarding receiving of assistance from God in crisis

Common people look forward to religion in times of crisis. Christians believe that genuine and sincere prayer is answered by God.

Table 16 Belief in Assistance from God in Crisis

Serial Number.	Belief in Assistance from God in crisis	Number	Percentage
1.	Always	27	90.00
2.	Never	1	3.33
3.	Don't Know	2	6.67
	Total	30	100.00

The table 16 points out that most of the respondents (90%) believed that they received assistance from God when they faced crisis in life.

Belief in God helps in facing challenges in life

It is said that no life can be imagined without difficulties or challenges. The believers often depend on God to overcome the difficulties.

Table 17 Belief in God helps in facing challenges

Serial Number.	Belief in God helps in facing challenges	Number	Percentage
1.	Yes	25	83.33
2.	No	1	3.33
3.	Not Sure	4	13.34
	Total	30	100.00

The table 17 suggests that a vast majority of respondents (83.33%) believe that they were assisted by God in facing challenges in life. It may be interpreted that the respondents got the strength and became confident to overcome the challenges by imposing faith on God.

Findings of the study

This study concentrated on the religious practices and beliefs of common people. The study was conducted amongst believers in Christianity in a rural set up. The researcher administered an interview schedule to conduct the survey. The data were collected and subsequently analysed. The objective of this chapter is to see whether this dissertation is successfully addressing the objectives of the study. The objectives mainly focused on understanding the perception of individuals on religion. Describing the religious practices as well as find out the place of religion in the lives of individuals.

It is evident from the age of respondents that wide range starting from eighteen to above sixty three years of age. But majority of them were youth members of community. The respondents had different educational status. Majority of the respondents have completed either secondary, higher secondary or graduation. It showed that respondents were literate. The respondents of the study belonged to different occupations. One third of the respondents were housewives. It can be said that in the rural areas women got married early and become housewives.

Majority of the respondents (96.67%) stated that they were committed to the religious teachings. Almost three fourth of the respondents (73.33%) told that they participated actively in the religious institution. All of them felt that they were religious. It is pertinent to mention that a significant percentage of people do not actively participate in religious institution but all considered themselves as religious.

Majority of the respondents (46.67%) believed that they were very much religious. Most of the respondents (46.66%) could not tell whether religion and spirituality carries same meaning or not.

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Majority of the respondents (70.00%) are visiting the same religious institution for more than twenty years. It is indicative of the fact that majority of the respondents were not very mobile and looking at the age distribution of the respondents, it can be assumed that they were visiting the religious place from an early age. It is to be noted that Christian ideals and teachings are generally introduced from an early stage of life through taking the child to the church and attending the Sunday schools organized by the Church. These schools provide catechism classes to the children to develop the believe system.

The duration mentioned by the respondents can be a sign of such long association with the Church since childhood. The religion of Christianity is based on scripture. It was found in this study that two third respondents study religious scripture. But it should be noted that a significant percentage (33.33%) did not study the scripture. It is also evident from the study that the reading habit varied significantly among the respondents. Only one fifth of the total respondents read it on a regular basis. As far as concept of God was concerned, majority of them believed that God is either ever present or forgiving.

The Christian religious teaching is also based on these fundamental beliefs. Hence, it can be said that they followed Christian teaching in expressing their opinion on the concept of the God. Majority of them (60.00%) believed in notion of heaven and hell. It was surprising to note that a significant number of respondents were not sure about it. Christianity teaches the existence of heaven and hell.

Overwhelming majority of them remembered God in the time of crisis. It can be said that for majority of the respondents, it was a refuge. Most of the respondents believed that they received help of God at the hour of crisis. The greater number of respondents (98.33%) felt that belief in God helped them to face challenges in life.

Limitations of the Study

The study was carried out in a village setup. The respondents were following Christianity. The village had also Muslim and Hindu families. They were not included in this study. This was the most prominent drawbacks as those people belonging to Hinduism and Islam, also practice religion in their everyday life. The researcher failed to show differences in the practices amongst different religions in that village community. The village life is more or less static. The mobility of the people is also limited. Hence, they can have religious practices without being influenced by the nature of their occupations. This can be very much different if the same study is conducted in the urban context. The mechanical solidarity arising out of religious practices in the everyday life was also not explored.

Conclusion

Religion and its practice continue to be part and parcel of life. People from different age groups perform religion. It is also true that organized religion lays down specific ways of performing it. But the people at their private domain also practices religion. The results of this study clearly show that religion has a very dominant position in the life of common people. In fact people try to follow the basic tenets of the religion. It

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is evident from the findings that people not only feel religious but also contribute to the religious institution. It is also revealed that many believers do not find opportunities to visit Church but they feel closer to the teachings of Christianity. The responses also show that God is considered as refuge in the context of problems of life. The belief of common people regarding intervention of God in the time of crisis shows the strong belief system exists in the Christian community.

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